

D-NOSES

Distributed Network for Odour Sensing,
Empowerment and Sustainability

D-NOSES

Events 3

D7.7 v1.1

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Deliverable

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Revision 1.0

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STATEMENT OF ORIGINALITY

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Summary

This document lists the events attended or organized by the D-NOSES consortium to promote, disseminate, and engage with different audiences in the third period of the project.

The last period of the project was largely characterized and limited by the pandemic conditions which were active for most of the period between April 2020 and September 2021. Due to these conditions, which included restrictions on travel and the number of people that could be hosted during meetings inside, it was realistically only possible to hold events online. Despite the limitations, it was still possible to participate and/or organize 29 events during this period.

- **Events for Public Audiences**

The D-NOSES team engaged with the public in **9 separate events**. The public engagement has always been important to the project due to the nature of the project and our desire to be responsive to the needs of the people. Where the public is concerned the motto was coined by MfC as “Nothing about them, without them”. Each event and exposure was another opportunity to gain more insight into the issues and the perceptions of the public. For this, we take the opportunity to thank the countless volunteers and generous souls that devoted time and effort to help this project with their data and their insights.

- **Events for Scientific Audiences**

In this last period, there were a total of **10 events** which included a scientific audience. As the project drew to a close, it was important to ensure the legacy of the work and bolster the scientific acceptance of citizen science as a valid and useful tool to obtain data as well as insights into complex problems such as odours. The events were mostly used to present the work and results of the pilots, as this is the basis of the validation of the method in scientific terms. The main message during these presentations is that the method can work in several different types of scenarios and should be applied depending on the context of the situation, sometimes in conjunction with more traditional methods.

- **Events for Policy Audiences**

The main objective of the project has always been to engage with policy makers and promote the idea that odour pollution needs to be taken more seriously, as it can have significant effects on the affected populations. Policy makers were addressed in **11 events** during the last period. The main message was that odour management and attendant regulations should be addressed at multiple levels, in a coherent and well balanced framework that works not only to resolve conflict situations in a fair manner, but hopefully also to avoid the problem in the first place with better informed planning processes. The focus of the policy engagement has been in

disseminating the policy brief, presenting the case for citizen science as a more balanced way of managing odour issues and stakeholder engagement as a healthier way for interaction during, but also before and after issues become acute. The good results and evaluation of the stakeholder engagement process during the pilots has been a key point in showing the value of the method towards policy. It is also heartening to see the several developments in pilot countries that are leading to the inclusion of odours into new environmental regulations, as well as new national standards.

The event for the EU Parliament stands out as a great achievement from the D-NOSES advocacy team. This event included representatives from across Europe and from each stakeholder group. The need for better regulation was discussed, as well as the suitability of citizen science to advance evidence based policy making - of course with a special focus on the D-NOSES methods.

- **Events for Industry Audiences**

The industry audience has been one of the more challenging ones to reach, as they have adopted in general a very defensive posture when it comes to odours. Industry audiences were present in **11 of the events during this period**. Engagement with industry during events has focused on promoting the method as a more cost-effective and practical way to deal with odour issues, as well as a good path to better risk management through community relations that help to avoid conflict. Through the interactions we have learnt that the way the stakeholders are brought to the discussion table is just as important as getting them there. For this reason the project has always maintained a neutral posture in its outreach to all stakeholders and emphasised the balanced nature of the approach.

- **Final Events**

To mark the end of the project phase the D-NOSES team was supposed to organise a final conference. To stay true to the project approach, it was decided to split this into 3 separate events to better target the audiences with the right content. The first event would be a general introduction, for the general public and lay audiences. The second would be an in depth look at the methods and results, focusing on content for scientific and industry audiences who would be interested in the practical details. The last one should then focus on policy makers, and present the work done towards advocacy and advancing the issue of better odour regulation.

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1. Events

Despite the problems and limitations of the pandemic, events remained a useful tool for D-NOSES to engage with the stakeholders and target audiences relevant to increasing the acceptance of the Citizen Science based odour management techniques. As before, this required engagement from the quadruple helix stakeholder sets, which included the public, policy, industry and research stakeholders.

As before, there were four main audiences targeted by the events, corresponding to the quadruple helix model of stakeholder engagement - the public, the industry, scientific community and the policy influencers. For each of these stakeholder groups, we present here a few reports from sample events.

- **Events for Public Audiences**

For the public, the events were largely focused on presenting the project and getting people to start using the App OdourCollect to map odours. These events fall outside of those that are organised to engage residents for specific case studies and are aimed at the general public to increase awareness and help fill the odour map with representative rather than strictly scientific data.

Events for the public, outside of the pilot activities, were more challenging to organise during the pandemic. This was largely due to the difficulties in reaching and interesting the public in showing up to a digital event. For this reason, most of the activities with public audience components were based on larger events that could draw the public in rather than organised by the project or its partners.

EU Green Week Exhibition

While the Green Week featured sessions mostly aimed at policy, it also featured an exhibition open to the public. This exhibition was largely meant to inform and create awareness in the public about the new green initiatives and developments. The 2021 edition was dedicated to “Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil” and delivered online between 1-4 June.

Figure 1. D-NOSES Digital Stand at the Green Week Exhibition Online

The purpose of the D-NOSES virtual stand was to exhibit the tools and resources the project produced and promote their use. The goal was also to display a coherent methodology that can also help convince policy makers that this is a viable system to drive community based environmental sustainability and health. The aim was to provide interactive sessions and activities that could be used both to educate visitors and collect feedback and data for the further refinement of the tools. On display was information on the OdourCollect app.

Figure 2. User guide of OdourCollect App

Further the stand was used to disseminate the Policy Brief, which is meant to help understand the issues and get to grips with how people can try to resolve them in their local context.

Figure 3. D-NOSES policy brief. English version.

For a general introduction the visitors were pointed towards the MOOCs (online training resource) that were created for the project. These, along with the other teaching materials and resources for schools, are meant to help educate kids on the issues and inspire them to become future citizen scientists.

We also took advantage of the time during the exhibition to engage in co-creation exercises with booth visitors to further refine the model for the International Odour Observatory site and improve it as a resource for future citizen scientists, passionate industries and engaged local authorities. There was also an idea to deploy a simulation in which visitors to the booth could role play the different stakeholders and define their actions and interactions with other stakeholders which would be represented by subsequent visitors to the booth. This would create a chain of simulated interactions that play out several pre-defined scenarios. Unfortunately, this was not successful due to lack of participation from visitors at the booth.

Figure 4. Virtual tour/ exhibition of D-NOSES

For the exhibition we created a virtual tour/exhibition of the project with information on the project as well as the experiences and results of the pilot cases. This was a 3d immersive

experience that could be followed independently by visitors. They could follow the automatic tour or take a stroll through the virtual space following their own path through the videos, posters, and stories of the project. The project reps of course were also on hand to engage and give explanations.

Figure 5. Virtual tour/ exhibition of cases studies D-NOSES project

● Events for Scientific Audiences

There were at least 10 events which targeted or included scientific audiences. The project consistently targeted scientific and research audiences as one of the key aspects of the project goals relies on citizen science being recognized and accepted as a formal and valid method of creating reliable data. To promote this, presentations and workshops during the events explained the methods and expanded on the results of the pilots to show under which conditions the D-NOSES approach can be most successful and valuable.

Citizen Science & SDGs Conference

One of the memorable events in this regard was the Citizen Science and SDGs Conference, which was the perfect platform to not only talk about the methods themselves, but also focus on their ability to contribute to the SDG and other policy goals in a meaningful way. Rosa Arias and Nora Salas Seoane from Ibercivis presented in the session for Citizen Science for health and well-being under the theme of Addressing global challenges.

Figure 6. D-NOSES presentation in Citizen Science & SDGs Conference

The presentation spoke about how D-NOSES for the first time considers the perception of odours of affected citizens and associated well-being to gather real-time odour observations that frame an objective view of the problem. The project aligns with SDG3, Good Health and Well-being, by guaranteeing a healthy environment and increasing the quality of life, contributing to target 3.9 reducing the deaths and illnesses from hazardous chemicals and air, water and soil pollution and contamination. Using citizen science and participatory strategies, citizens can build collaborative odour maps through the OdourCollect App, which contributes to promote dialogue between public authorities, industries, and academia – quadruple helix model – to co-create innovative solutions to increase air quality and improve their well-being.

Further it was illustrated how at a practical level, the project with 10 pilots in 9 countries in Europe, Chile and Uganda could improve the health and well-being of citizens by influencing policies at the local, national, and global levels. The presentation listed the successes like how one of the pilot countries is already drafting a national law to regulate odour pollution, and in Spain, a working group is drafting a standard for using citizen science to monitor odour pollution. Moreover, the presenters explained how D-NOSES is also undertaking research on the effect of frequent exposure to odours and the related chemicals to health and how these initiatives contribute to target 3.d from SDG 3 strengthening the capacity of all countries for early warning, risk reduction and management of national and global health risks.

In another session, the team from MfC, Louise Francis, Hannah Stockwell and María Alonso-Roldán presented their work done in creating and maintaining the International Odour

Observatory as a resource to promote innovative solutions to persistent environmental odour issues around the world.odour

Figure 7. International Odour Observatory presentation in Citizen Science & SDGs Conference

Finally, the D-NOSES team, including Simone Rufenacht (ECSA), Nora Salas Seoane (Ibercivis) and Lucia Paz Errandonea (IfC) held a special workshop on Highly Inclusive Engagement in Citizen Science, under the provocative headline “You have the buzzwords, but do you have the people?”. The workshop highlighted how the D-NOSES methodology ensures inclusivity in its activities by design, and then went on to illustrate each phase and its challenges using the experiences from the pilot case study in the Forum Area in Barcelona. Experiences and interesting approaches taken in the other pilots from the D-NOSES project were then shared to demonstrate the range of approaches and creative thinking that is sometimes necessary to truly be as inclusive as you hope to be.

Figure 8. Workshop on Highly Inclusive Engagement in Citizen Science & SDGs Conference

NOSE 2021 Conference

Another significant event for the D-NOSES team was the NOSE 2021 Conference where several presentations were given by project partners. This world-class event provided very interesting programmes with the opportunity to exchange ideas with colleagues from all sectors, including academia and industry, and share presentations of the latest key innovations within Environmental Odour Monitoring & Control. The 7th International Conference on ENVIRONMENTAL ODOUR MONITORING & CONTROL originally scheduled in Taormina, was held in pure virtual format. Three presentations featured the project work during the pilots on odour measurement and management and stakeholder engagement methods. The presentations focused on the pilot design, the implementation, and results. Finally, there was another presentation on the work to create a new national standard in Spain.

All these online presentations were recorded and were made available through the D-NOSES website as well the project YouTube channel to expand their reach. Below we also report the number of views received since the event.

- *Improving the Impact of Odour Nuisance: A stakeholder Engagement Approach*

Stavros Vlachos from D-NOSES partner Envirometrics presented the pilot carried out in Thessaloniki, Greece. (33 views on Youtube Channel)

The Greek Pilot - Thessaloniki

- Second most populous city in Greece and densely populated (approx. 7100 ppl/sq-km)
- A city with multiple complaints for odour nuisance over time
- Not well defined boundaries between industrial and urban areas
- Citizen groups organized (environmental orientation)
- Willingness of the local authorities to participate

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Figure 9. Greek pilot presentation in Nose 2021 Conference

- Outcomes of a citizen science methodology and traditional odour impact evaluation techniques

Gerhard Schleenstein from D-NOSES partner ECOTEC presented the pilot carried out in Los Alamos, Chile. (24 views on YouTube Channel)

Results: Odour annoyance – Questionnaires

Questionnaire method

- June 2019 (purpose not revealed)
- Model questionnaire: core questions (K)
- Total sample: 55
 - Acceptable response: 41
 - Excluded due to implausibility: 6

Results

- Spatial distribution apparently represents well plume
- Insights on focusing efforts on citizen engagement

Survey zone	Villa Esperanza	Villa Caupolicán (close to source)	Villa Caupolicán (distant to source)	Kintupi Ruca
Arithmetic mean	1.8	5.7	1.7	3.4
Standard deviation	3.2	3.4	2.6	3.2
Min/Max	0/9	0/10	0/5	0/8
Median	0.0	7.0	0.0	3.5

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Figure 10. Chilean pilot presentation in Nose 2021 Conference

- *The results of the Barcelona Pilot*

Rosa Arias, from D-NOSES partner and coordinator Ibercivis, presented the pilot carried out in Barcelona, Spain. (31 views on YouTube Channel)

Figure 10. Spain pilot presentation in Nose 2021 Conference

- *New Spanish Standard for Collaborative Odour Maps*

Cyntia Izquierdo from D-NOSES partner AMIGO talked about the work done to develop a new national standard for the use of the Collaborative Odour Maps to better manage odour issues. (40 views on YouTube Channel)

Figure 11. New Spanish Standard for collaborative Odour Maps presentation in Nose 2021 Conference

Events for Policy Audiences

Events for policy audiences were based on promoting the new and multi-level governance models that D-NOSES believes is necessary to improve the management of odours. The events helped to disseminate the policy brief and make the case that odour pollution is not just nuisance but can also have significant effects on health and standard of living.

- EU Parliament Event – Revisiting Odour Pollution in Europe

Figure 12. EU Parliament Event- Revisiting Odour Pollution in Europe

The main policy directed event of the project was the webinar organised in collaboration with the European Parliament Intergroup on 'Climate Change, Biodiversity and Sustainable Development' and its chair, MEP Maria Spyraiki. The event was meant to bring together policymakers, representatives from industries, communities, and scientists to present their perspective on the issue, also based on the Green Paper on Odour Pollution. The discussion on the Green Paper outlined the main challenges of regulating odours and put forth recommendations towards an improved policy framework for odour pollution, which should include the multi-level governance model developed by D-NOSES.

Figure 13. The potential of Citizen Science to inform environmental policies presentation (by Mr. Sven Schade) in the EU Parliament event.

At the event the D-NOSES concept was presented as one of the possible solutions to better manage odours, complementing the existing more traditional methods. The focus was on the need for policies and standards that should allow and help select the right tool for the job given the specific context and requirements. An introductory presentation by Sven Schade from the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission explained how citizen science has a natural place in the growing move towards evidence-based policies. Rosa Arias then introduced the D-NOSES methods, and how it fits in a strategic move to better odour governance.

The strategic roadmap for Odour Governance

Scope and purpose

Governments and environmental authorities have a complex task in the application of odour regulations and guidelines. There are as many approaches as countries and sometimes the **lack of a strong legislation minimizes citizens' protection.**

The **Strategic Roadmap for governance in odour pollution** serves to inform policymakers about the context and situation regarding odour pollution in Europe, focusing in the D-NOSES countries, which can inspire the development of a robust legislation framework on the matter.

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Figure 14. Revisiting Odour Pollution in Europe: D-NOSES contribution presentation (by Rosa Arias) in EU Parliament event.

The panel discussion included Dr. Laura Capelli, Associate Professor at the Department of Chemistry, Materials and Chemical Engineering, in Politecnico di Milano representing the scientific community. Benoit Zerger, Team Leader for Industrial Emissions, C4 Unit on Industrial Emissions & Safety, DG ENV was there to provide a policy perspective. Meanwhile, Silvina Frucella, President of AireNet Association from the D-NOSES Barcelona Pilot, gave voice to the affected populations and reiterated the need for more to be done to protect them. Joachim Quoden, Chairman of the International Solid Waste Association (ISWA) European Group and Managing Director of the Extended Producer Responsibility Alliance (EXPRA) provided an industry context to the discussion and stressed that better planning and environmental licensing processes are an essential component in the mix to avoid problems in the first place. Finally, Marieke Schouten, Alderman of the Municipality of Nieuwegein, Rapporteur of the Committee of the Regions opinion on the EU Action Plan: 'Towards Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil', Committee of the Regions (CoR) who committed to considering whether the CoR should propose to include odour pollution in the action plan.

Figure 15. Revisiting Odour Pollution in Europe: D-NOSES contribution presentation (by Rosa Arias) in EU Parliament event.

It is hoped that the event will give momentum to the discussion on implementing better policies towards the management of odours within the European Union. This will require follow-up and further discussions that will fall outside of the official scope of this project.

- *APEA International Webinar on Citizen Science for monitoring odours in waste and water sector*

This webinar organised by APEA took place on the morning of April 27th, 2021. It was focused on discussing citizen science as a method for odour monitoring in the water and waste sectors. The session took place over three hours and was attended by representatives from the entire quadruple helix. Between 80 to 90 participants attended and the event was considered a success due to the interesting and useful discussions.

The first session consisted of two presentations about best practices in odour management; the first one explaining the LIPOR case study regarding waste management and the second one presenting the measures applied in the WasteWater Treatment Plant of Alcântara in Lisbon.

This was followed by an introduction to the D-NOSES project, presented by Rosa Arias, and a quick interactive exercise was carried out to glean a better understanding of the advantages of citizen science in odour monitoring from the different perspectives of the attendees.

In the third session, the results of three different pilots of D-NOSES were presented: the Italian pilot by Laura Capelli, the Chilean pilot by Gerhard Schleenstein and the Barcelona pilot by Rosa Arias. They explained the different results and the specific characteristics of each location. It was followed by a quick workshop where the OdourObservatory webpage was presented during which participants were asked for their professional perspectives in relation to relevant and useful content within the Observatory, which was led by Mapping for Change.

International Odour Observatory

I am a local resident and...

I want to know if there is an European regulation which defines limits for odour emissions from poultry farms.

I work for a waste/ waste water company and...

I would like to learn from previous waste water treatment plants in order to adopt the best practice for my plant and reduce citizens' complaints for future developments.

I work for a public administration and...

I would like to know if I can use an electronic nose to measure the level of annoyance of a waste water plant that we manage.

I am a researcher and...

I would like to know whether Citizen Science can support data collection for environmental monitoring across different domains?

 D-NOSES #dNosesEU #odourObservatory

Figure 16. International Odour Observatory workshop in APEA International Webinar on Citizen Science for monitoring odours in waste and water sector

A roundtable moderated by the Project Coordinator comprised of two representatives of the Waste and Wastewater sectors in Portugal, an APEA member, and the Environmental Officer of Kampala City Council Authority (Uganda) made up the final session of the day. It was a very productive discussion thanks to the diversity of participants and the ideas gathered. The industry attendants commented on the complementarity of the methodology and the importance of engaging affected communities, meanwhile the KCCA officer remarked on the importance of the data collected for allocating the limited resources of the council. Finally, the Webinar was closed by Inês Costa, the Secretary of State for the Environment of Portugal, who reaffirmed the commitment of the Portuguese Government regarding air pollution and inherently addressing odour pollution.

Events for Industry Audiences

For the project to be successful it is also necessary for odour generating industry to be aware of the method and be given a chance to use it. During events targeting the industry, the main objective was to create awareness and stress the unique selling points of the D-NOSES methods that include the near real-time data, the positive engagement with the local population and the cost-effective nature of the concept.

- *Rethinking Waste*

Figure 17. Rethinking Waste 2020 event

Since odours are frequent in waste management installations, the project was featured in a stand created to promote EU H2020 projects during the Rethinking Waste 2020 event organised by ISWA and Waste Management World magazine.

The stand consisted of the standard communication and dissemination downloads, the video playing in a loop, and of course a representative available for questions and discussions on the project.

Figure 18. D-NOSES Stand in Rethinking Waste 2020 event

Downloads and Views during the two day exhibition:

Table 1. Downloads and views of D-NOSES tools in Rethinking Waste 2020 event

D-NOSES Brochure	19
D-NOSES Policy Brief	17
D-NOSES Roll-Up/Poster	17
Innovation Showcase - D-NOSES Video	130

The interest in the D-NOSES project was reasonably high relative to the total exposure of the event which received about 500 visitors from the waste industry. In that regard, for example the D-NOSES video views accounts for a quarter of all visitors. From there, we see about 15% of those watching the video went on to download the materials. There were 9 people who actively engaged with the stand representatives to ask questions and learn more about the project, though most of these were individuals attending the exhibition based on professional interest in the waste industry rather than company representatives. Nevertheless, there was enough personal interest which we believe will eventually translate to corporate interest as awareness further penetrates the industry.

Final Conferences

In keeping with the identified stakeholder audiences used across the events throughout the project, the final conference was also split to target three different groups. It was thought that it would be better to present the project at different levels depending on the target audience, and that it would not be useful to make different groups sit through presentations not relevant to them. The three final conference events were therefore split up into:

1. General Public / Introduction to the Project D-NOSES
2. Scientific Community / Presentation and Exploration of the Methods
3. Policy Makers / Presentation and Discussion on the Policy Goals and Actions

The three events were planned to be on separate days, though always within a few days of each other to maintain momentum.

- *Introduction to D-NOSES*

This general introduction to the project was aimed at the public and/or other stakeholders that were interested in the project at a more superficial level. It also served as an introduction to the project with a little taste of everything, and visitors could then choose to join us in one, or both, of the next events to get the full picture of the project and its results.

This first event in the series got 79 online registrations resulting in a total attendance of 62 on the day of the event.

Figure 19. *The D-NOSES project at a Glance!.. D-NOSES Final Conference*

At the start, former D-NOSES Project Officer Warin Colombe talked about how multi-actor approaches to research are now being favoured in the way that project proposals are being appraised and selected.

Figure 20. *D-NOSES Project Officer presentation in D-NOSES Final Conference*

The program went through all the main points of the project and the pilots, quickly explaining the methodology, the engagement model and the tools created.

Figure 21. The D-NOSES tools presentation in D-NOSES Final Conference

After this, the pilots were presented, with a few minutes each to give a short description of the work done and the results achieved in each one.

Figure 22. Italia pilot presentation in D-NOSES Final Conference

Towards the end the program focused on giving the attendees a basic understanding on how the D-NOSES methods could be applied in other communities affected by odour. This was based on the replicability guidelines, and a short interactive workshop to engage with the attendees.

DIY guidelines for citizen science projects in odour-conflicted communities

- Supporting citizen science projects to tackle odour issues in odour-conflicted communities.
- Helping you to 'do it yourself'.
- Offer tested tools and practical tips for running projects and adapting them to different contexts and other socio-environmental challenges

Open & available to everyone soon at The Odour Observatory!

NEW

DIY guidelines for citizen science projects in odour-conflicted communities

Figure 23. The D-NOSES DIY replicability guidelines presentation in D-NOSES Final Conference

The participants were reminded and encouraged to use the resources to be found on the International Odour Observatory, which contains all the tools and guidelines so that anyone can start planning and executing their own citizen science based odour management intervention in their own local area.

At the end, attendees were also invited to come back for the next session on D-NOSES methods and policy actions if they wanted a deeper dive into the project.

- *D-NOSES Methods*

LIVE WEBINAR

The D-NOSES methodology and results to tackle odour pollution using citizen science

October 18

11:00-13:00 & 14:00-16:00 CEST

In this second session of the final conference that took place on the 18th of October 2021, the focus was clearly set on the methodology, its validation through the pilots and an evaluation of the results and practical lessons learned during the project.

This second session in the D-NOSES final conference series garnered 53 registrations for the event with a total attendance of 42. This was lower than the first session, but the technical nature of this event makes this result unsurprising.

Figure 24. The D-NOSES methodology and results to tackle odour pollution using citizen science. D-NOSES Final Conference

In the first part of the event, the methodology was explained and examined as one of the options available to odour management practitioners when choosing a tool set to work with. As with all tools, the D-NOSES methods have advantages and disadvantages compared to other more traditional methods. The suitability of the method is dependent on the context, and Laura Capelli (POLIMI) explained when and how to use it, emphasizing that it is a methodology complementing the others and not replacing them.

Figure 24. The advantages of citizen science to monitor odour pollution presentation in D-NOSES Final Conference

The next part of the conference featured an in-depth look at five of the pilots and their results. This included the pilots in Barcelona, Italy, Chile, Greece and the UK. After a short question and answer session, it was time for lunch.

After the lunch break, the next part investigated some of the aspects that were important to the success of the pilots. For example, the need for some validation of the data being created, and the odour training required for the citizens to produce more reliable results.

Figure 25. Data validation and data plausibility presentation in D-NOSES Final Conference

Then there were presentations on the educational aspect of the activities during the project in which school children were involved in activities and were taught about odours and their possible role in managing them through citizen science. Finally, this section was closed with a talk on how to ensure inclusiveness during the pilot interventions and in general, something which could be quite challenging given some of the local conditions.

The last hour of the event was devoted to a general evaluation of the methodologies and their effectiveness, followed by a round table discussion in which project participants were able to discuss their experiences and key learnings from their own pilots. The last 15 minutes Rosa Arias, D-NOSES project coordinator also talked about the legacy of the project and how all the tools and results will remain available at the International Odour Observatory after the project.

- *D-NOSES Policy Goals and Actions*

In the third webinar of the final Conference on Odour Management & Citizen Science, the D-NOSES team focused on the work and activities performed during the project to help introduce odour pollution and its management into the policy agendas across Europe and beyond. It was planned to be a platform to address citizen science to influence Policy, the regulatory framework as well as highlight the need of a standard methodology.

There were 80 registrations in total and 59 attended on the day.

Figure 26. *Introducing odour pollution in the policy agendas. D-NOSES Final Conference*

The first part of this event was used to present how citizen science is fast becoming an important tool in measuring and exploring complex issues to inform policy makers. Speakers focused on the impact citizen science can have on environmental policies, but also how it can be used to help achieve some of the Sustainable Development Goals.

The next section dealt with the multi-level governance model advocated by the D-NOSES team. First a complex picture of the current state of regulatory frameworks was sketched, making it quite clear that the difference from country to country, region to region and even city to city can be enormous.

Figure 27. The Challenges of regulation odours: The case of Metropolitan Area of Barcelona in D-NOSES Final Conference

Representatives from the Barcelona local government spoke about the challenges they face in regulating odours. Rosa Arias then introduced the multi-level governance model, and discussed the key learnings from trying to apply it during the project.

Figure 28. The D-NOSES Multilevel Governance Model in D-NOSES Final Conference

After the lunch break the advocacy actions and policy results achieved during the project were presented and celebrated. This included the ongoing work to prepare the Spanish national standard for the use of citizen science for tackling odour issues, the advances made towards a

new odour regulation in Portugal, the new regulatory framework in Chile that identified odour as a pollutant.

Finally Rosa Arias presented the Green Paper on Odour Pollution, and the way forward after the end of the project. This was followed by a short question and answer session, after which she thanked the participants and stakeholders in the project for their contributions over the last 3 years.

Figure 29. The D-NOSES Green Paper in Odour Pollution D-NOSES Final Conference

- *Legacy*

The final conference, despite the descriptor, will not be that final. For that reason we also avoided using that name and billed it a Conference on Odour Management. The International Odour Observatory will continue past the life of the project, and the passion and dedication of the consortium partners will remain. All of the partners will undoubtedly stay supportive of the mission and lend a hand where they can in future endeavours.

In fact, for all their efforts in the last 3.5 years, we are truly thankful to all the consortium members and their invaluable contributions to the whirlwind of events - the count of which now exceeds over 100 in total. We firmly believe it has been this commitment to promoting the project and the methodology on the ground that has had the most impact on getting buy-in and engagement from the quadruple helix stakeholders.

2. List of Events Attended

The D-NOSES team has continued in its attempts to maintain an active events strategy where the project could be presented online either directly or as a part of a larger event. The table below lists the many events at which the consortium members presented and represented the project over the last period, including partners and names of the presenters/participants from each institution, location, dates, event type, activity undertaken and its brief description and the number of attendees. By tracking the audience types and visitors we can help track the possible impact and level of dissemination of the project.

Table 2. List of all events attended by D-NOSES Consortium since Events 2

Name of Event (with link where possible)	PARTNER and name of the attendees	Location	Date	Event type	Activity	Visitors	Audience Type
Public screening of Southall Odour Documentary	MfC Maria Alonso, Perrine Machuel, Lousie Francis, Hannah Stockwell	Online	09/07/2020	Public meeting	Promote the use of OdourCollect and the protocol devised by CASH members, create momentum for the collection of data	48	Industry, Policy, Public
Citizen Science for environmental monitoring	MfC Maria Alonso, Perrine Machuel, Lousie Francis, Hannah Stockwell	Online	21/07/20	Webinar	Promote citizen science for odour monitoring including OdourCollect	35	Policy,
ECSA2020 conference	MfC, IFC, ECSA, IBERCIVIS Maria Alonso, Lucia Errandonea, Simone Rufenacht, Louise Francis, Hannah Stockwell, Rosa Arias, Nora Salas	Online	06/09/2020-10/09/2020	Conference	D-NOSES poster and Workshop on engagement methodology	400	Scientific community

European Research and Innovation Days	D-NOSES NA	Online	22/09/2020 to 24/09/2020	Video shown in the Exhibition	We proposed the Barcelona Video to the Exhibition and then they include D-NOSES in the video link I have pasted https://vimeo.com/556147573/5a53c176f7	6000	Policy
Rethinking Waste	ISWA Jose Uribe	Online	22 and 23/09/2020	Exhibition	Participation in H2020 project booth for dissemination of materials and networking	500	Industry
CS & SDGs Conference	IBERCIVIS, IFC, MfC, ECSA, MIO, ISWA, ECOTEC Rosa Arias, Nora Salas, Lucia Errandonea, Simone Rufenacht, Maria Alonso, Louise Francis, Jose Uribe, Gerhard Schleenstein	Online	14 and 15/10/2020	Conference	Oral Presentation, 3 posters and marketplace stand	500	Scientific community
Ecomondo 2020	ISWA Jose Uribe	Online	03.11.2020 - 06.11.2020	Exhibition	Online Booth and digital materials dissemination		Industry
Citizen Engagment Festival EC	IBERCIVIS, IFC Rosa Arias, Nora Salas, Lucia Errandonea	Online	6/12 to 10/12 2020	Exhibition	Video		Public
Webinar on CS financial sustainability	IBERCIVIS Rosa Arias	Online	19/11/2020	Conference	Oral presentation about the financial sustainability of D-NOSES with the exploitation of results Plan and the creation of Science for Change		Scientific community

COMENSI project international multiplier event	MfC Hannah Stockwell, María Alonso	Online	10/12/2020	Conference	Presentation, stakeholder engagement method introduced using the example from Barcelona	24	Public
Citizen Science event	IBERCIVIS Rosa Arias, Nora Salas	Online	21/01/2021	Workshop	Oral Presentation of the project.		
Introduction to Citizen Science & Scientific Crowdsourcing - UCL course	IberCIVIS, MfC Rosa Arias, María Alonso	Online	27/01/2021	Other	Oral presentation of the OC and IOO.		Scientific community
XXXVII Congreso Interamericano de Ingeniería Sanitaria y Ambiental	ECOTEC Gerhard Schleenstein	Online (Bs. As. Argentina)	12/04-2021-15/04/2021	Conference	Oral presentation of the D-NOSES project and the pilot study in Chile.	300	Industry
NOSE2020	AIDIC Rosa Arias, Carlos Díaz, Gerhard Schleenstein, Beatrice J, Stavros Vlachosa, Izquierdo Cyntia	Online	18/04-2021-21/04/2021	Conference	Oral presentations of the D-NOSES project and the pilot studies.	55	Scientific community
Odors & Air Pollutants 2021 - Water Environment Federation	ECOTEC, AMIGO Gerhard Schleenstein, Carlos Díaz	Online (Cincinnati, Ohio, USA)	20/04-2021-23/04/2021	Conference	Oral presentations of the D-NOSES project and the pilot studies.	120	Industry
APEA International Webinar on Citizen Science for monitoring odours in waste and water sector	IBERCIVIS, POLIMI, ECOTEC, APEA, MfC Rosa Arias, Laura Capelli, Gerhard Schleenstein, Pedro Santos, Luis Marinheiro, Louise Francis...	Online	27/04/2021	Other	Oral presentations of the D-NOSES project and the pilot studies.	157	Industry, Policy, Scientific community
Final Event Barcelona Pilot	IBERCIVIS, IFC Rosa Arias, Nora Salas, Lucía Errandonea	Online	29/04/2021	Other	D-NOSES final Event pilot Bcn & citizen contribution	11	Public

WSIS Forum	MfC María Alonso, Louise Francis	Online	03/05/2021	Conference	Present different uses of tech to achieve SDGs - Kampala pilot example	50	Public, Industry, Scientific Community, Policy
APEA International Webinar Odours Monitoring and Treatment	APEA, POLIMI, IBERCIVIS, AMIGO Laura Capelli, Rosa Arias, Carlos Diaz	Online	31/05/2021	Workshop	Odour monitoring and abatement techniques	125	Industry, Policy, Scientific community
Green Week EU	ISWA, MfC, IBERCIVIS Jose Uribe, Florence Kuijl	Online	1/06/2021-04/06/2021	Exhibition	Booth dedicated to the project to disseminate materials and information.	5300	Public
Southall and Hayes Roundtable	MfC Maria Alonso, Louise Francis, Hannah Stockwell, Ben Duncan	Online	03/09/2021	Roundtable	Present findings and open dialogue to reach a consensus for next steps	12	Policy, Industry, Public, Scientific Community
Congreso de Ciencia Ciudadana Chile	Ciencia Ciudadana Chile Rosa Arias	Online	02/09/2021 - 03/09/2021	Conference	Citizen Science	70	Public
Community Engagement - Science Camp	MfC Louise Francis	Online	10/09/2021	Conference	Promote the engagement method - success and failure in UK- and citizen science	13	Scientific community
VDI Konferenz "Gerüche in der Umwelt"	AMIGO Carlos Diaz	Wiesbaden, Germany	24/11/2021-25/11/2021	Conference	D-NOSES results	100-150 (tbc)	Industry, Policy
9th IWA Conference on environmental odour management	olores.org & IWA Rosa Arias, Carlos Díaz, Cyntia Izquierdo	Bilbao, Spain	26-27/11/2021	Conference			Industry, Policy, Scientific community
The D-NOSES Project at a glance!	All Partners	Online	14/10/2021	Conference	Conference style presentation of the D-NOSES project targeting a lay audience.	62	Public
The D-NOSES Methodology and Results to tackle Odour Pollution using Citizen Science	All Partners	Online	18/10/2021	Conference	Conference style presentation of the D-NOSES project methods for a scientific audience.	41	Scientific Community

Introducing Odour Pollution in the Policy agendas	All Partners	Online	20/10/2021	Conference	Conference style presentation of the D-NOSES project activities aimed at introducing odour pollution into the policy agenda.	53	Policy
EU Parliament Event - Revisiting Odour Pollution in Europe	MIO-ECSDE, Ibercivis, Polimi, ISWA Anastasia Roniotes, Rosa Arias, Laura Capelli, Jose Uribe	Online	28/10/2021	Webinar	Inform and promote citizen science and the D-NOSES methods for odour management within a multi-level governance model to an EU policy maker audience.	144	KM

3. Event Materials

- [D-NOSES Affected Communities Map](#)

The screenshot shows the 'D-NOSES Affected Communities Map' interface. On the left, there is a sidebar with the title 'Odours Affecting Communities' and a sub-header 'Añadió hace 2 años'. Below this is a 'Categorías' section with a list of categories: 'Mostrar todo', 'Waste Management', 'Waste Water Treatment', 'Agriculture/Livestock', 'Food Industries', 'Industrial', 'Urban Odours', and 'Unknown'. Each category has a checkbox and a dropdown arrow. The main area is a map of Europe and Africa with several circular markers containing numbers: 69 (Ireland), 55 (Germany), 13 (Portugal), 66 (Italy), 16 (Turkey), and 22 (Kenya). The map includes navigation controls like zoom in/out, pan, and search.

- [D-NOSES Policy Brief](#)

Available in various languages (English, Spanish, Italian, Portuguese, Greek, German, French, Bulgarian)

D-NOSES
Distributed Network for Odour Sensing, Empowerment and Sustainability

ODOUR POLLUTION A GROWING SOCIETAL CONCERN

HIGHLIGHTS

- Odour nuisance, being the second cause of environmental complaints after noise, lead to a significant decline in our quality of life and must be urgently addressed.
- Odour regulations across Europe and within countries differ significantly from each other. In many places they are even completely lacking. There is a need for bottom-up multi-level governance in Europe in order to protect its citizens.
- Odorous gases are commonly measured at the source (emission). The level of the odours in surrounding residential areas (inmission) is more complex to determine, but also much more relevant to measuring the impact on residents.
- The Distributed Network for Odour Sensing, Empowerment and Sustainability (D-NOSES) project will reverse the way in which odour pollution is commonly tackled, through a co-creative citizen science approach.

MAIN ODOUR ISSUES IN EUROPE

The sources that generate odours in European communities are numerous and diverse; in many cases the same community is exposed to more than one odour source. Industrial activities, waste management and agriculture/livestock represent the main challenges regarding odour emissions within Europe.

HOW TO CITE

D-NOSES consortium (2019) Odour Pollution - A growing societal concern. D-NOSES Policy Brief #1

Authors: Simone Röllnick (ECMA), Clément Guillet (ECMA), Alex-Abou Daher (MNO-ECSE), Annette Bröcher (MNO-ECSE), José Uribe (ISWA), Nuno Sales Soares (IBERCIVIS), Ravi Anand (IBERCIVIS).

This policy brief was facilitated by the lead authors (ECMA) through open interaction and discussion with the D-NOSES consortium. While this was carried out as part of H2020 D-NOSES Coordination and Support Action project, the views expressed in it do not reflect the consensus opinion of D-NOSES partners.

D-NOSES
Distributed Network for Odour Sensing, Empowerment and Sustainability

POLUIÇÃO POR ODORES UMA PREOCUPAÇÃO SOCIAL CRESCENTE

DESTAQUES

- Os odores desagradáveis, sendo a segunda causa de queixas ambientais a seguir ao ruído, conduzem a um declínio significativo da nossa qualidade de vida e devem ser urgentemente abordados.
- Os regulamentos sobre odores na Europa e entre países diferem significativamente uns dos outros. Em muitos locais, são mesmo totalmente inexistentes. É necessária uma governação "bottom-up" e a vários níveis na Europa, de forma a proteger os seus cidadãos.
- Os gases odoríferos são geralmente medidos na fonte (emissão). O nível de odores nas áreas residenciais circundantes (emissão) é mais complexo de determinar, mas também muito mais relevante de forma a medir o impacto nos residentes.
- O projecto Distributed Network for Odour Sensing, Empowerment and Sustainability (D-NOSES) inverterá a forma como a poluição por odores é normalmente abordada, através de uma abordagem de co-criação da ciência cidadã.

PRINCIPAIS ODORES NA EUROPA

As fontes que geram odores nas Comunidades Europeias são numerosas e diversas; em muitos casos, a mesma Comunidade está exposta a mais de uma fonte de odor. As atividades industriais, a gestão de resíduos e a agricultura/livestock representam os principais desafios que se diz respeito às emissões de odores na Europa.

COMO CITAR

Consortium D-NOSES (2019) Odour Pollution - Uma preocupação crescente da sociedade. D-NOSES Policy Brief #1

Autores: Simone Röllnick (ECMA), Clément Guillet (ECMA), Alex-Abou Daher (MNO-ECSE), Annette Bröcher (MNO-ECSE), José Uribe (ISWA), Nuno Sales Soares (IBERCIVIS), Ravi Anand (IBERCIVIS).

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Coordinated by: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 789215

Coordinated por: Este projeto recebeu financiamento do Programa de Investigação e Inovação Horizon 2020 da União Europeia no âmbito de Convenção de Subvenção 789215

D-NOSES
Distributed Network for Odour Sensing, Empowerment and Sustainability

ЗАМЪРСЯВАНЕТО НА ВЪЗДУХА С МИРИЗМИ НАРАСТАЩ ОБЩЕСТВЕН ПРОБЛЕМ

АКЦЕНТИ

- Неприятните миризми във въздуха са втората причина за оплаквания, постъпили от граждани, след шума в световен мащаб. Те могат да значително повлияват на качеството на живот и трябва спешно да бъдат взети под внимание.
- Регулациите по отношение на миризмите в Европа и извън нея варират и са различни за всяка държава. На много места дори липсват такива. Ние имаме за цел да направим европейски нава в Европа, за да бъдат предпазени гражданите.
- Обикновено газовете се измерват при техния източник (емисия). Нивото на миризмите в околните райони (имисия) е по-сложно да се определи, но и много по-важно за измерване на въздействието им върху жителите на тези райони.
- Проектът "Управление на миризмите при производствени съоръжения на отпадъци" (D-NOSES) ще промени начина, по който традиционно се справяме със замърсяването с миризми, чрез съвместените усилия на учени и граждани.

ОСНОВНИ ПРОБЛЕМИ, СВЪРЗАНИ С МИРИЗМИТЕ В ЕВРОПА

Източниците, които генерират миризми в европейските области, са многобройни и разнообразни. В много случаи едни и същи области е изложени на повече от един източник на миризми. Промислените дейности, управлението на отпадъците и одикото стопанство представляват са основните предизвикателства по отношение на имисията на миризмата в Европа.

ЦИТИРАНЕ

Консорциум D-NOSES (2019) Замърсяването на въздуха с миризми - нарастващ обществен проблем. D-NOSES Кратко описание на политиката №1

Автори: Simone Röllnick (ECMA), Clément Guillet (ECMA), Alex-Abou Daher (MNO-ECSE), Annette Bröcher (MNO-ECSE), José Uribe (ISWA), Nuno Sales Soares (IBERCIVIS), Ravi Anand (IBERCIVIS).

This policy document is a synthesis of findings from ECMA pilot activities and discussion shared with the consortium D-NOSES. While this was carried out as part of H2020 D-NOSES Coordination and Support Action project, the opinions that it does not express are not reflecting the consensus of D-NOSES partners.

D-NOSES
Distributed Network for Odour Sensing, Empowerment and Sustainability

POLLUTION OLFACTIVE UNE PRÉOCCUPATION SOCIÉTALE CROISSANTE

FAITS SAILLANTS

- Les nuisances olfactives, deuxième cause de plaintes environnementales après le bruit, entraînent une baisse importante de notre qualité de vie et doivent être traitées de toute urgence.
- Les réglementations en matière d'odeurs en Europe et à l'intérieur des pays diffèrent considérablement les unes des autres. Dans de nombreux endroits, ils sont même complètement absents. Il est nécessaire de mettre en place une gouvernance ascendante à plusieurs niveaux en Europe afin de protéger ses citoyens.
- Les gaz odorants sont généralement mesurés à la source (émission). Le niveau des odeurs dans les zones résidentielles voisines (inmission) est plus complexe à déterminer, mais aussi beaucoup plus pertinent pour mesurer l'impact sur les citoyens.
- Le projet D-NOSES (Distributed Network for Odour Sensing, Empowerment and Sustainability) vise à inverser la manière dont la pollution olfactive est généralement combattue, grâce à une approche co-créative de la science et la société.

PRINCIPAUX PROBLÈMES D'ODEURS EN EUROPE

Les sources qui génèrent des odeurs dans les communautés européennes sont nombreuses et diverses ; dans de nombreux cas, la même communauté est exposée à plus d'une source d'odeurs. Les activités industrielles, la gestion des déchets et l'agriculture/élevage représentent les principaux défis concernant les émissions d'odeurs en Europe.

COMMENT CITER

D-NOSES consortium (2019) Pollution Olfactive - Une préoccupation sociétale croissante. D-NOSES Policy Brief #1

Autores: Simone Röllnick (ECMA), Clément Guillet (ECMA), Alex-Abou Daher (MNO-ECSE), Annette Bröcher (MNO-ECSE), José Uribe (ISWA), Nuno Sales Soares (IBERCIVIS), Ravi Anand (IBERCIVIS).

Cette synthèse a été facilitée par les auteurs principaux (ECMA) grâce à une interaction et une discussion ouvertes avec le consortium D-NOSES. Bien que cela a été réalisé dans le cadre du projet H2020 D-NOSES Coordination and Support Action, les opinions qui y sont exprimées ne reflètent pas l'opinion du consensus des partenaires D-NOSES.

Coordinated by: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 789215

Coordinated por: Ce projet a été financé par le programme de recherche et d'innovation Horizon 2020 de l'Union Européenne dans le cadre de la convention de subvention n° 789215.

● Updated Version of the D-NOSES Brochures - For Communities

Join the conversation!

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 @dNOSES_EU
 dNOSES.EU

Coordinated by:

Funded by the Horizon 2020 programme of the European Union
Grant Agreement No 789315

● **Co-creating alternative solutions to odour pollution**

D-NOSES is an EU H2020 funded project that aims to provide a bottom-up approach to tackling odour pollution issues.

The project introduces new mapping, data collection and community engagement tools to facilitate citizen science interventions across Europe and beyond. Data will be collected in *The International Odour Observatory*, a platform dedicated to promoting engagement at all levels, and literally putting odour pollution on the map. Through participatory strategies and citizen science, D-NOSES will co-create local solutions with citizens, industries, regional & local authorities and odour experts in at least 10 pilot sites to build up a multi-level governance model in odour pollution.

From April 2018 to March 2021, and with a 3,1 M€ budget, D-NOSES will produce the *Green Paper on Odour Pollution*, scientific and policy guidelines, and a *Strategic Roadmap on Odour Pollution* to introduce the issue into the policy agenda and help promote sustainability through community action.

● **Citizen science for sustainability & governance**

Did you know that odour pollution is the second reason for environmental complaints after noise across Europe? Does it affect your community?

Odour pollution has repeatedly been ignored in the policy agendas, leaving citizens defenceless. D-NOSES will empower citizens through an innovative bottom-up approach to increase transparency and enhance positive relationships within communities, as well as increase quality of life.

D-NOSES will produce real-time data to inform the co-creation process with all stakeholders. Odour observations will be gathered using:

The free mapping app **OdourCollect**

The collaborative **Community Maps**

Get involved!

● **D-NOSES Brochures - For Industry**

Join the conversation!

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 [dNOSES.EU](https://www.facebook.com/dNOSES.EU)

Coordinated by:

Funded by the Horizon 2020 programme of the European Union Grant Agreement No 789315

● **Co-creating alternative solutions to odour pollution**

D-NOSES is an EU H2020 funded project that aims to provide a bottom-up approach to tackling odour pollution issues.

The project will introduce new mapping, data collection and community engagement tools to facilitate citizen science interventions across Europe and beyond. Data will be collected in *The International Odour Observatory*, a platform dedicated to promoting engagement at all levels, and literally putting odour pollution on the map. Citizens will then join other stakeholders such as industries, local authorities and NGOs, in at least **10 pilot sites** to co-create solutions for their odour problems.

From April 2018 to March 2021, and with a 3,1 M€ budget, D-NOSES will produce the *Green Paper on Odour Pollution*, scientific and policy guidelines, and a *Strategic Roadmap on Odour Pollution* to introduce the issue into the policy agenda and help promote sustainability through community action.

● **Citizen science to improve the management of industrial odours**

Is your industry emitting odours that have an impact on communities?

Engage with D-NOSES to produce **real-time data** through citizen participation. Odour observations gathered using the **free mapping app OdourCollect** will allow you to optimise your industrial process to reduce impact and to check the effects of any newly implemented good practices and corrective measures. Co-created data will be validated by a world-class team of odour experts and made available on the **Odour Observatory** maps. All this at a fraction of the cost of traditional odour studies.

Our innovative methodology uses a bottom-up approach that will increase transparency and enhance your relationship with the communities and environmental authorities.

● **OdourCollect Application Brochure**

Are you experiencing any problem?

Contact us or report any incidence through the app

You can also contact us via email odourcollect@ibercivis.es

Become a super citizen scientist!

- Interact with other users
- Look up the odour map
- Be part of a pilot case study

odourcollect.eu @Odourcollect odourcollect

Funded by the Horizon 2020 programme of the European Union Grant Agreement No 789315

OdourCollect App

OdourCollect is the free app to report your odour observations. In the European project D-NOSES, we are using it in 10 countries to build up collaborative odour maps.

Contribute by reporting your odours in the map!

You can also add odours through the website odourcollect.eu. If you have any questions or would like to report an area where odour nuisance exists, please contact us on odourcollect@ibercivis.es.

How to download the app

Access GooglePlay (Android) or the AppStore (Iphone) and type OdourCollect

How to report a new odour

To report an odour, you have to follow the steps:

- 1 Add a new odour.
- 2 Choose the type of the odour perceived (if you have doubts, you can always guess).
- 3 Score the odour intensity.
- 4 Score how pleasant or unpleasant is the odour.
- 5 Add the duration of the odour episode. You can also add any comments.

User guide of the OdourCollect App

Smell and share!

OdourCollect is part of the D-NOSES project

dnoses.eu

Sign in

To register you must enter your email, username and password. Keep in mind that when registering, you will receive an email to verify your account. Don't forget to verify it!

NOTE: The app or website will ask you for access to your location so that the observations you make will be added to the map wherever you are.

● **Roll Ups**

D-NOSES
Distributed Network for Odour Sensing,
Empowerment and Sustainability

Co-creating alternative solutions to odour management issues

ABOUT THE PROJECT

D-NOSES is an innovative project that includes citizens in a collaborative approach to improve traditional odour management.

Foto by Vero Photoart in Unsplash

INVOLVEMENT

D-NOSES will connect affected communities with local authorities, industries and experts in a platform to co-create solutions to odour problems.

STRATEGY

Combining citizen science, new methods for mapping, data collection and local engagement, D-NOSES will help citizens in the co-creation of local solutions together with stakeholders.

The new bottom-up approach increases transparency, improves community relationships and increases quality of life through practical and creative ideas.

TAKE PART

Would you like to know more about odours in your neighborhood, where they come from and what you can do about it?

Register and Participate!

- 1 Together we will learn to identify odours
- 2 Help us gather real time observations using the free App OdourCollect
- 3 To understand the odour sources that impact your area we will use scientific models to validate your observations
- 4 Contribute to the co-creation of solutions together with neighbors, industries, public authorities and odour experts

App OdourCollect
dnoeses.eu

WHERE

The project will focus on 10 specific pilot case studies around the world, but anyone can register to start adding observations for their local area and replicate the method in their own neighborhood.

Pilots will take place in at least these countries around the world:

Greece			
Chile			

RESULTS

- International Odour Observatory
- 10 case studies in 10 countries to validate the D-NOSES methodology
- Put odour pollution on the policy agenda at a global, national and local level
- Policy briefs to inform new regulation
- Green Book on Odour Pollution
- Strategic Map of Odour Pollution

● Posters (Scientific)

D-NOSES
 Distributed Network for Odour Sensing,
 Empowerment and Sustainability

Co-creating the International Odour Observatory

Authors: R. Arias & N. Salas (Ibercivis Foundation [Spain]), M. Balestrini & L. Errandonea (Ideas for Change [Spain]), L. Francis & M. Alonso-Roldán (Mapping for Change [UK]), and J. Uribe (International Solid Waste Association [ISWA, Austria]).

OUR PURPOSE

Odour pollution is the second leading cause of environmental complaints after noise¹, and yet, remains relatively ignored in environmental regulations. Many communities have had to tolerate odour nuisance for decades, with no hope of action being taken.

D-NOSES aims to implement *Principle 10* of the Rio Declaration² by engaging citizens and building capacity for action based on a bottom-up approach. The project relies on the best of possible sensors to measure odours: people's own nose. With Citizen Science tools, such as *OdourCollect*, pilot communities can map and measure the problem. Armed with scientific, validated data, people will be empowered to become their own driving force for change. Following a quadruple helix model, citizens and stakeholders will co-design local solutions, which will filter up to a multi-level governance framework that can ultimately be used to introduce odour pollution into the policy agenda.

OUR METHODOLOGY

D-NOSES aims to improve on existing engagement methodologies from project partners Ideas for Change (IFC) and Mapping for Change (MfC) through a comprehensive field evaluation of different methods. A combined approach will enable D-NOSES to create a reliable, replicable method that should be universally applicable in diverse regions and situations around the globe, to generate scientifically valid and actionable data through citizen science interventions that can improve people's lives.

Our engagement methodology

The *Bristol Approach*³, as developed by IFC, puts the concerns of citizens at the very heart of the process, helping local communities to co-design and implement citizen science based interventions around matters of concern in their living areas, such as odour pollution, which lead to creative solutions and positive results. This ensures a high level of sustained engagement throughout the duration of the project, as citizens are prepared to give their time and energy to address matters that are relevant to the community.

Our inclusive citizen science approach

The *engagement model by MfC*⁴ is deliberately flexible to follow different pathways directed by discussions and needs of the local community. Guided by *Principle 10*, the model starts by introducing already existing and accessible information. Then it follows up with a facilitation process that supports communities to collect and share their own environmental data from citizen science observations. The generated data is then evaluated and improved in an iterative loop so that it can finally support the drive for change.

Our inclusive citizen science approach

With local needs and culture at the forefront, the *Extreme Citizen Science approach*⁵ provides communities with a means to not only monitor their surrounding environment and analyse their findings but to also define the problem, co-design methodologies and tools that enable them to own, share, and act on their results. Our citizen science interventions are intrinsically inclusive and apply all the *Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)* dimensions, with a special focus on the gender and science education aspects.

OUR 10 PILOT INTERVENTIONS

■ Countries where pilots will take place
■ 3 extra pilots to be decided

1 COORDINATOR: Ibercivis Foundation, Spain
2 Ideas for Change, Spain
3 Mapping for Change, UK
4 MfC-ECIDE, Greece
5 International Solid Waste Association, Austria
6 AMIGO, Spain
7 Politecnico di Milano, Italy
8 University of Kassel, Germany
9 APEA, Portugal
10 Envirometric, Greece
11 Ecotec, Chile
12 São João da Madeira Municipality, Portugal
13 Municipality of Sola, Bulgaria
14 LIPOR, Portugal

BOARD MEMBERS:
15 Mr. Alexander Jara (INFP), Kenya
16 Ms. Corina Ecsedi (MfC), Washington
17 Mr. Stephen Sze (CEU), Hungary
18 Ms. Andrea Sanhueza (P10 expert), Chile
19 Mr. Mark Roper (ICMARS), Morocco
20 Mr. Tsun Okunai (INEMA), Uganda
21 Mr. Gloria Sanchez (AMBA), Spain
22 Mr. Carlos Borrego (MfC), Austria
23 Ms. Nuno Barata (ISWAMC), Portugal
24 Mr. Nuno Lucas (AFA), Portugal

OUR RESULTS

From April 2018 to March 2021, and with a 3,1 M€ budget, D-NOSES will produce:

- The International Odour Observatory
- The Green Paper on Odour Pollution
- Scientific guidelines for policy-making
- The Strategic Roadmap on Odour Pollution
- DIY guidelines for project replicability

REFERENCES

¹ Pollutions olfactives: origine, législation, analyse, traitement. L'Agence de l'environnement et de la maîtrise de l'énergie (ADEME). D'après 2005.
² Paris, access Principle 10 and The Bali Guidelines at United Nations Environment Program #1 <http://web.unep.org/about/majorgroups/partnerships/participation-information>
³ Balestrini, M., et al. (2017) "A city in common: a framework to orchestrate large-scale citizen engagement around urban issues." Proceedings of the 2017 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems, ACM.
⁴ Håklay, M., and Francis, L. (2018). Participatory GIS and community-based citizen science for environmental justice action. In Chakraborty, J. Walker, G. and Holbrook, B. (Eds.), The Routledge Handbook of Environmental Justice. Abingdon: Routledge, pp. 297-308
⁵ Håklay, M. (2019) Citizen Science and Volunteer Geographic Information: Overview and Typology of Participation. In: Sui, D., Goodchild, M. (eds) Crowdsourcing Geographic Knowledge. Springer, Dordrecht. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-4562-2_7

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D-NOSES MOOC on Odour Pollution for the Public

This MOOC invites you to explore the not so-well-known problem of odour pollution. During this 'journey' you will have the opportunity to understand what generates the problem of odour pollution and how it affects our lives. You will also examine its impacts - environmental, social, health and economic. Last but not least, you will get informed on what we can do as citizens about the issue and what are the available tools for tackling the problem. The MOOC is developed in the framework of the D-NOSES Project: "Distributed Network for Odour Sensing, Empowerment and Sustainability" that aims at introducing odour pollution in the policy agendas. D-NOSES has received funding from the European's Union Horizon 2020 Science with & for Society Call (SwafS) under grant agreement No. 789315.

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